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project

D5.8: DAP validation

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Deliverable Review and Approval

The individuals listed below are not directly involved in the preparation of this deliverable and will review the present document.

Name	Organisation

Executive summary

The subject of this deliverable is the validation of the Decision Analytics Platform (DAP), obtained through a meeting held in Bari with the main stakeholders and institutional decision-makers of the Apulian case.

After an introduction about the participants and the structure of the meeting, Deliverable D 5.8 provides the report of the presentations made.

The first presentation outlines the methodology adopted and the tools produced, introducing the main keywords and orientation elements for reading the results.

The purpose of the second is to share the data and information collected, the hypotheses made, and the results obtained.

Finally, in the third, a live demonstration of the use of the IT platform was offered.

The meeting ended with a discussion on the limits and potential of the results and tools, identifying potential extensions, and collecting some willingness to support further system developments.

Acronyms and abbreviations

AIP:	Autorità Idrica Pugliese
ANN:	Artificial Neural Network
AQP:	Acquedotto Pugliese
ARPA:	Agenzia Regionale per la Protezione Ambientale (Regional Agency for Environmental Protection)
DAF:	Decision Analytics Framework
DAP:	Decision Analytics Platform
DM:	Decision-Maker
DPS:	Direct Policy Search
EIPLI:	Ente per lo sviluppo dell'Irrigazione e la trasformazione fondiaria in Puglia, Lucania e Irpinia (Organization for the development of irrigation and land transformation in Puglia, Lucania and Irpinia)
GIS:	Geographic Information System
GCM:	General Circulation Model
ICT:	Information and Communication Technologies
ID:	Irrigation District
IPCC:	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ISPRA:	Istituto superiore per la protezione e la ricerca ambientale (Higher Institute for Environmental Protection and Research)
IT:	Information Technology
LSTM:	Long short-term memory
MOEA:	Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithm
RCM:	Regional Circulation Model
RCP:	Representative Concentration Pathway
RNN:	Recurrent Neural Networks
WP:	Work Package
WP:	Water Planning Portfolio

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1 Introduction

The methodology and the main results were presented and discussed on 23/11/2022 at the headquarters of Acquedotto Pugliese in Bari in a final meeting entitled "Project Ô: Multi-objective analysis of the impacts of climate change in complex systems. The case demonstration of the Apulian Aqueduct". The purpose of the meeting was to get a validation of the process and tool developed by Project Ô.

The meeting had, as topics, the introduction of the concepts and objectives of Project Ô, the description of the methodology used, and the presentation of the tools developed to face the challenges of climate change in managing water resources. The models, the scenarios of the climatic and socio-economic drivers produced, and the mitigation and adaptation actions identified were presented. In addition, a demonstration of the IT platform implemented was provided to support the comparative analysis of water portfolios.

The meeting ended with a discussion about the potential transfer of the developed technology to the local institutions and the practical interest in using these tools.

Meeting participants were both project partners and relevant stakeholders, representatives of the following entities:

- Acquedotto Pugliese,
- Autorità di Distretto dell'Appennino Meridionale,
- Consorzio della Capitanata,
- Consorzio Terre d'Apulia,
- EIPLI,
- Regione Puglia.

2 The outlines

The following sections contain what was presented to stakeholders and decision-makers using the slides (in Italian to facilitate understanding), which are reported in the appendices.

2.1 Introduction and methodological issues

Each sentence in this chapter refers to the individual slides contained in Appendix 1.

The slide features a light blue background with a white header section. In the top left, it displays the Horizon 2020 logo and the project ID 'H2020-CIRC-2017 - 776816'. In the top right, it shows the date 'Bari, 23/11/2022'. The main title 'project' is written in a lowercase, sans-serif font, accompanied by a circular logo with a water drop and waves. Below the title is the subtitle 'demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water'. The central text reads 'Project O: Analisi multi-obiettivo degli impatti del cambiamento climatico nei sistemi complessi. Il caso dimostrativo di Acquedotto Pugliese'. To the right, it says 'Inquadramento metodologico'. At the bottom left are the logos for 'POLITECNICO MILANO 1863' and 'Fondazione Politecnico di Milano'. At the bottom right, the names of the presenters are listed: 'Andrea Castelletti, Marco Micotti, Matteo Sangiorgio, Enrico Weber'.

The context: in a changing world, the demand for resources is growing, and climate change increases the frequency of extreme events.

Project Ô considers reuse (water loops), integrating it with the other elements that make up the system, and trying to move from a purely centralized perspective in managing resources to the composition of local small water loops considering a circular model.

The case study concerns the extended system on which the Apulian Aqueduct stands, an emblematic example considering the size, complexity, and level of sharing of resources.

The analysis cannot be limited to the current scenario, but future scenarios must also be considered (hydro-meteorological projections of inflows and socio-economic water demand).

Responding to climate challenges and growing needs requires additional availability and decision-support tools. Project Ô produces 2 decision support platforms: the User Collaborative Platform (UCP) dedicated to the industrial sector and the Decisional Analytic Platform (DAP), designed for public decision-makers.

The DAP framework schematizes the overall system thanks to a series of elements: the identification of the set of institutional actors (decision makers) and stakeholders; the selection of interventions and possible relevant decisions (actions); and the identification of scenarios of climatic and socio / economic forcing. This process must be faced having in mind quantifiable and shared objectives, to which indicators are added to quantify the impact of the various actions on the points of interest.

In the case of AQP, the overall objective is to assess whether integrating unconventional water sources into traditional water management practices can guarantee the satisfaction of present and future needs. For this purpose, a strategic model was built. This model aims to capture the complexity of the water system while ensuring computational efficiency that allows the use of optimization algorithms (optimal control) considering 4 objectives to be minimized: drinking, irrigation, industrial water deficits, and the adduction process cost.

The project benefited from a detailed model of the AQP (Aquator) adduction system, which has been simplified using surrogate modeling techniques and then integrated into the general framework.

The methodology involves 3 phases:

1. the generation of hydro-meteorological and socio-economic scenarios;
2. the construction of the decision-making platform (strategic model, optimization engine, mechanism to manage uncertainty);
3. the production of efficient portfolios from the point of view of objectives, looking for compromises that guarantee stakeholders' satisfaction.

The generation of climate scenarios consists of using a modeling chain to pass from general circulation models (GCMs) to regional ones (RCMs) and then adapt them to local measures with statistical downscaling techniques.

The study analyzed the effects of two climate scenarios (RCPs): 4.5, which is moderate compared to the expected thermal increase and 8.5, which is considered extreme. Furthermore, two reference horizons were considered (2050-2059 and 2090-2099), two patterns of the drinking water demand of the users served by AQP, and two reuse scenarios with which to expand the overall availability of water.

The comparison between different solutions has been performed using a particular tool based on the "parallel plot", a graphic representation where the vertical axes (4 in our case) represent the indicators reflecting the stakeholders' interests. Each line reported in the plot represents a possible portfolio we can adopt.

When considering only 2 dimensions, the parallel plot can be visualized through a classic scatter plot that provides a more convenient visualization of the trade-off between the concurrent sectors using the concept of Pareto efficiency as the basis of the identification of excellent portfolios.

The final part of the meeting was dedicated to the presentation of the decision support platforms, in particular the DAP, which has the institutional sector as its interlocutor. DAP includes a series of interfaces linked to our models that allow the users to interactively visualize the results obtained from portfolio simulations.

3 Summary of the information collected, and the main results obtained

Each sentence in this chapter refers to the individual slides reported in Appendix 2.

The slide features a light blue background. At the top left, it displays the Horizon 2020 logo and the project ID 'H2020-CIRC-2017 - 776816'. To the right, the word 'project' is written in a lowercase, sans-serif font, accompanied by a circular icon with a water drop and waves. Below this, the text reads 'demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water'. The date 'Bari, 23/11/2022' is in the top right corner. The main title, 'Project O: Analisi multi-obiettivo degli impatti del cambiamento climatico nei sistemi complessi. Il caso dimostrativo di Acquedotto Pugliese', is centered in a large, bold, blue font. To the right of the title, the subtitle 'Aspetti modellistici e implementativi' is written in a smaller, blue font. At the bottom left, there are logos for 'POLITECNICO MILANO 1863' and 'Fondazione Politecnico di Milano'. At the bottom right, the names of the project members are listed: 'Andrea Castelletti, Marco Micotti, Matteo Sangiorgio, Enrico Weber'.

One of the project's challenges consisted in reducing the complexity of real systems for implementation and computational purposes. In some cases, such as the irrigation distribution networks (for example, considering the Ofanto and Agri-Sinni schemes), it was used as context information to better understand the system, but then the model did not explicitly represent it. In others, the AQP drinking water supply networks were represented in an aggregate manner with the modeling reduction techniques described below, allowing its explicit representation within the strategic model.

The meeting illustrated the results concerning:

- the estimation of availability, presenting the models of the inflows to the reservoirs and that of the natural springs;
- the estimation of the needs, that is, of the irrigation applications of reference to each reservoir, of the industrial demand at the Monte Cotugno reservoir, and, finally, of the drinking demand.

To obtain these results, a lot of effort was dedicated to collecting data, starting from the weather data available both as measures (by ARPA, the irrigation consortia, and AQP) and as the output of publicly available reanalysis models.

The inflows to the reservoirs were obtained by closing the water balance (defined by a mass-balance equation) relative to each reservoir and processing data provided by AQP, Consorzi, and ARPA.

The needs were instead estimated starting from the reports of the Basin Authority, crossing this information with the values obtained by processing the historical supplies provided by AQP, Consorzi, and R. Puglia.

Finally, the strategic model makes use of simulation models of large reservoirs, representing their physical and structural characteristics.

Under the supervision of the University of Palermo, AQP spa built a complete model of its distribution network a few years ago, using a well-known commercial software produced by Oxford Scientific, Aquator, that simulates complex water resource systems with a daily time-step and computes an optimal allocation. The AQP model represents the current hydraulic scheme and the existing pumping and hydropower systems and purification plants

of the available sources. However, this would lead to huge computational costs (a computing time greater than 4000 days for a 10-year horizon and 10,000 function evaluation, a relatively small number for a many-objective problem as the one at hand), making the problem practically intractable due to the high number of simulations required to find reasonable results in the optimization procedure.

A widely adopted method to solve this issue consists in building a surrogate model (sometimes named also response surface, reduced model, or emulator) to replace the original one. The surrogate model is not required to describe the physical processes with the same level of detail as the original high-fidelity model it surrogates. Its aim is to reproduce the relationship between a set of input variables (i.e., the water flows released into the aqueduct) and a corresponding set of outputs (drinking water deficit and the distribution costs) in a straightforward and computationally efficient way.

The implementation of a surrogate model usually follows these steps:

1. input/output samples generation via design of experiments: the creation of synthetic series of flow rates introduced into the network (from reservoirs and sources);
2. simulation of the original high-fidelity complete model of the distribution network by replacing the reservoirs with catchments and obtaining the optimal allocation;
3. processing Aquator results to calculate:
 - a. overall deficit;
 - b. total costs;
4. training a neural network selecting the surrogate structure, and optimizing its parameters;
5. testing phase and evaluation of the accuracy of the surrogate.

In the first phase, we generate the input/output pairs running multiple parallel simulations of Aquator. These data constitute the dataset used in the surrogate model identification process. The second step requires selecting a suitable architecture for the reduced model and training it. Machine learning models are usually adopted for this aim due to their flexibility, high accuracy, and computing time performance. Here we adopt Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) with a feed-forward structure, implemented in Python programming language using Keras, a high-level open-source library that provides an interface for TensorFlow. While the main routine for simulation and optimization is in C++, we rebuilt the network avoiding any possible source of inefficiency in the program execution.

We obtained high accuracy, R^2 higher than 0.99, with a limited number of neurons, 8. The performance index further confirms that the surrogate model is not overfitting the values obtained by the Aquator simulation. Conversely, the surrogate has high precision and generalization capability.

To obtain optimal operating policies for water systems, we adopted a simulation-based optimization to iteratively improve the operating policies based on the simulation outcome, generally named Direct Policy Search (DPS), recently extended to solve multi-objective problems by using Multi-Objective Evolutionary Algorithms (MOEAs).

This approach produced an ensemble of optimal policies for each combination of water demand, climate projection, temporal horizon, and eventual unconventional water reuse technologies adopted.

3.1.1 Baseline

The baseline scenario is a snapshot of the hydro-climatic and socio-economic conditions for the historical decade (2010-2019). No unconventional water reuse technologies are currently in use, and thus they are not considered in this scenario. To compute the water deficits of the irrigation, industrial and drinking sectors, the demands were estimated for all the users.

The core result of the analysis is the Pareto front visualized using a parallel axes plot representation. It allows us to appreciate the trade-off between the highly competing four objectives (all to be minimized): irrigation, industrial, drinking deficits (first, second and third vertical axes), and potable water distribution cost (fourth axis).

The trade-off between the three deficits (agricultural, industrial, and drinking) is highly competitive since the three users would use the same water resources from shared reservoirs. Due to the water scarcity regime in the region, the water volume available is insufficient to satisfy all the water demands simultaneously. Consistently, the parallel plot shows that the policies that guarantee a low deficit for one of the water users do not produce satisfying values for the other competing sectors.

Parallel plots allow visualizing the trade-off between an arbitrary number of objectives. However, the interpretation of the results is usually much more critical than in the case of a 2-dimensional plot. To this point, we can rule out the fourth axis of the parallel plot (representing the drinking water distribution cost) since they are charged to urban water users and are thus covered by the bills. We aggregate the irrigation and industrial water deficit to simplify the visualisation further.

Beyond the representation of the trade-off, we are also interested in selecting some policies that are significant for the case at hand. For instance, we aim to find a compromise policy that leverages the benefits of all the considered sectors. To do that, we first select all the policies that guarantee performance in the top 10% of the range of the drinking deficit. Among them, we chose the best policy in terms of irrigation deficit. Another significant operating strategy for our analysis is the one that prioritizes the drinking deficit.

The system operated with a specific policy can then be simulated so that we can understand its impact. All the reservoirs present the same periodic pattern: the water inflows during wintertime (a period of null agricultural demands and low drinking demand) are stored in the reservoirs reaching high water levels during spring. The combined effect of low inflows and high water demands causes a decrease in the reservoirs' level till October/November.

In the considered 10-year time horizon, 2012 and 2017 represent two cases of extremely dry years. The effect of these droughts can be easily spotted in the deficit trajectory of Occhito and Pertusillo. Their deficit is quite low, with the only exceptions of 2012 (for Occhito) and 2017 (for Pertusillo). Interestingly, the considered policy seems to be able to distribute the deficit between these two districts using a sort of coordination mechanism, thanks to the possibility of partially compensating for the availability of water for drinking. In this way, at least partially, it is possible to free up resources for irrigation use. In general, the irrigation district served by Conza reservoir emerges as the most vulnerable to droughts. Its deficit under the selected operating policy is not negligible even in particularly wet years and is exacerbated in critically dry years (i.e., 2012 and 2017). Monte Cotugno reservoir is the only one distributing water to all the considered sectors, i.e., irrigation, industrial and potable. The pattern recorded for the industrial deficit is low in the first part of the simulation and worsens starting from 2017. This is even more evident looking at the irrigation deficit: it is almost negligible until 2016, while severe water shortages are registered from the following year.

The baseline scenario analyzed in the previous section is not fully coincided with the historical conditions. For instance, it strictly respects the constraint relative to the Environmental Flow (EF). However, the current management of the reservoirs only respects the EFs imposed by the Italian and European legislation in case of water abundance. During the water-scarce periods, the legislation is not always respected to reduce the deficit (especially for the drinking section, which is usually prioritized). We thus repeat the optimization for the baseline scenario imposing to respect the constraint related to EFs.

Not considering the EF constraints, a relevant water volume becomes available and is used to satisfy the water demands of the three considered sectors. The Pareto front thus moves down-left, producing a better performance for both the objectives and the shape of the yellow front (always below $0.5 \text{ (m}^3/\text{s)}^2$ for the irrigation and industrial squared deficit) indicates that the trade-off between the drinking sector and the other users is strongly reduced with respect to the baseline.

3.1.2 Future climate scenarios

The identification of robust operating policies requires considering not only historical hydro-meteorological and socio-economic data but to extend the analysis to a set of possible future scenarios that have to represent the

future variability of the processes at hand (in this case, the inflows into the reservoirs and the flows of the two natural springs).

We use the future climate scenarios provided by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) in the fifth Assessment Report (AR5) in 2014, which have become a standard in the field of climate modeling and research in the last few years. The IPCC report presents four Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs), each one describing a different climate future depending on the greenhouse gas (GHG) concentration trajectory. For each RCP, it is possible to compute the corresponding increase (with respect to the period from 1850 to 1900) in the global surface temperature.

In our analysis, we consider two RCPs. A moderate scenario represented by RCP 4.5, which is described by the IPCC itself as an intermediate scenario, and an extreme scenario, RCP 8.5, generally taken as the basis for worst-case analysis (in the last decade, RCP 8.5 has been thought to be very unlikely, but still possible).

These future climate projections are generated at the global scale and are used as input for global and regional models to generate variables such as temperature and rainfall. Since our strategic model takes as input water flows at the local scale, it is first necessary to downscale the projections of temperature and precipitation, from large to local scale, and then to estimate a relationship between these variables and the water flows.

The first step is performed using a traditional statistical downscaling method, the quantile mapping. Quantile mapping techniques are a bias correction method that removes possible systematic errors in the global circulation models (GCMs) or regional circulation models (RCMs). Once the downscaling transformation is identified for the control period (2006-2019 in our case), it can be applied to correct the bias of the large-scale dataset in future periods as well.

Once the temperature and precipitation projections have been downscaled, estimating the relationship between these two variables to the water flows is necessary. Following the same approach of quantile mapping, the relationship must be estimated on historical data and then applied to future time series.

This relationship is usually estimated by means of physically based models, ranging from basic rainfall-runoff models to more complex implementations, such as the HBV models, that describe the dynamics of the different processes (such as those related to snow, soil moisture, or the routing) through dedicated routines. However, the lack of reliable datasets for the area of interest in terms of temporal coverage and data quality prevents a satisfactory calibration of the parameters. In addition, as we already pointed out, the inflow time series for the historical period is estimated by inverting the water-balance equation, thus deriving the net inflow (inflow minus the losses, such as evaporation). Net inflow can assume negative values, especially during summertime when evaporation is greater than the flow drained by the hydrological basin, that cannot be directly modeled with HBV models since they require modeling the losses with specific sub-models.

To directly derive the net inflow from temperature and rainfall, we follow an empirical data-driven approach (specifically the ANNs) instead of the traditional physical one. A good model of the inflow keeping track of the past input values to produce a suitable estimation of the target variable is a recurrent neural network (RNN). We consider a specific type of recurrent neuron, the LSTM cell.

For each reservoir (or natural spring), an LSTM model is identified on the historical data (from 2010 to 2019). We are not interested in forecasting the historical time series with high accuracy, thus reproducing, for instance, the timing and the exact value of each peak. Our neural model has to be a good synthetic generator, meaning that more than the timing and punctual values, it has to reproduce the statistical properties of the historical time series.

Once the LSTM models have been identified on the historical period, they can also be applied to the future, considering as input the climate projections that we previously downscaled to the local scale. As said, the future climate has a key role in our analysis since it drives the changes in the hydro-meteorological regimes, and thus the water availability. In our analysis, we consider a moderate (RCP 4.5) and an extreme (RCP 8.5) climate scenario and two future periods (2050-2059 and 2090-2099).

First, we analyze the combined effect of future climate and the respect (or not) of the constraint related to the EFs. For the sake of simplicity, we report the results only for RCP 8.5 in the mid-term horizon (2050-2059). Comparing the Pareto fronts of the baseline scenario with the RCP 8.5 in the mid-term period (in both cases with and without the application of EFs), it is clear that the decrease in water availability due to climate change will dramatically affect all the sectors. This situation becomes even worse when considering the EFs following the legislation: the front moves up-right, and its points are widely spread, meaning that the conflict between sectors is strongly exacerbated.

As already done for the baseline, for each scenario, we consider a compromise solution that balances the trade-off between the objectives and a top-drinking policy that prioritizes the drinking sector (minimizing its deficit). For instance, under current climatic conditions, the drinking deficit grows from 34.7 Mm³/year to 47.3 Mm³/year due to the imposition of EF constraints. The combined effect of EF and future climate further increases the deficit to 71.8 Mm³/year. When considering the top-drinking policies, the same analysis can be done: the drinking deficit in the situation closer to the current conditions (baseline without EF) is 22.0 Mm³/year and is expected to become 56.4 Mm³/year (more than doubled, +156%) due to the climatic and legislative variations.

3.1.3 Future drinking demand

Beyond the variability of the hydro-meteorological conditions due to climate change, which affects the inflows to the system, it is necessary to consider the future changes in the drinking demand pattern. In a recent study, the Apulian water authority (Autorità Idrica Pugliese, AIP) defines a future pattern reflecting expected socio-economic changes. The projections are mainly driven by tourism development, which will strongly increase the drinking water demand on the coastline on the one hand and concentrate the request during summertime (the traditional holiday period in Italy) on the other.

In the previous section, we quantified the effect of EF constraints, that are not fully respected in the current management. However, following European legislation, EFs will have to be considered in the future (they should have already been considered). We thus decide to consider EF in our analysis from now on.

The combined effect of the future pattern of the drinking demand and climate conditions produces a sensible deterioration with respect to the front obtained in the baseline. Interestingly, three out of four Pareto fronts (RCP 4.5 2050-2059, RCP 4.5 2090-2099, and RCP 8.5 2050-2059) are almost overlapped. This is somehow in accordance with the IPCC projections of global surface warming, which estimate a temperature increase between 1.5°C and 2°C for RCP 4.5 as well as for RCP 8.5 (but in the mid-term, say before 2060). Conversely, the temperature increase is expected to be more than 4°C for RCP 8.5 at the end of the century. To give an idea of the magnitude of estimated changes, we can consider the drinking extreme of the fronts. The drinking deficit grows from 31.4 Mm³/year (corresponding to 1 m³/s) to around 150 Mm³/year (4.5 m³/s) under the more conservative scenarios and around 200 Mm³/year (6 m³/s) in the case of the more severe scenario.

3.1.4 Water reuse technology

The water balance in the region will be affected by two concurrent terms. First, a remarkable water volume will be lost because of the new hydrological regime. Second, the water demand will increase due to the future socio-economic development of the region. These changes require mitigation actions to reduce the pressure on freshwater resources. We here consider and implement two strategies for water reuse: wastewater reclamation for irrigation and industrial use and reactivation of dismissed wells.

The quantification of the potential water volume to be reclaimed in the Apulia Region, as well as the specific sites where the reclamation technologies can be used in the future, have been investigated in the Project Ô Deliverable D5.7 (Economic and operational analysis of technology adoption through case studies). We integrate the relevant elements that emerged from this analysis in the context of our modeling framework by associating each plant mentioned in the D5.7 to an irrigation or industrial district considered in our model. Each water reclamation plant is then indirectly implemented to reduce corresponding demand. The reduction corresponds to the quantity of water provided by water reclamation and thus must be fulfilled with freshwater resources. The percentage of water

reduction for agriculture is remarkable only for the districts linked to Occhito (31.54 Mm³/year) and Locone (3.94 Mm³/year) reservoirs. In the other irrigation districts, the reduction seems negligible compared to the demand, but produces an overall saving of 13.88 Mm³/year. In the industrial district associated with the Monte Cotugno reservoir, the future water demand drops to zero because the water reuses fully satisfy the water demand. The water reuse relative to each irrigation and industrial district produces an overall freshwater saving of 61.97 Mm³/year.

An additional water source that can be used to mitigate the effect of the future hydrological regime, as well as the new demand pattern, is the reactivation of dismissed wells. We identified seven wells that had been dismissed due to the critical conditions of the aquifer (saltwater intrusion and the percolation of pollutants have been identified as the two major causes of groundwater quality deterioration). The overall freshwater available assumed here is 9.46 Mm³/year.

The situation obtained under future scenarios is extremely critical and would cause remarkable environmental, economic, and social issues. In this context, it is fundamental to be able to quantify the effect of water reuse technologies that can help mitigate the combined effects of climate change and of the new drinking demand pattern. The Pareto fronts obtained with the implementation of non-conventional water reuse technologies allow for estimating the impact of these water loops.

Even if the situation is remarkably improved, the effect of water reuse implementation is far from entirely closing the gap with the baseline. This means that the specific mitigation actions adopted here are not sufficient and that it is necessary to further promote the spread of reuse technologies.

4 Demonstration of the platform and description of its architecture

Each sentence in this chapter refers to the individual slides contained in Appendix 3.

The slide features a light blue background. At the top left, it displays the project ID 'H2020-CIRC-2017 - 776816' and the Horizon 2020 logo. At the top right, it shows the date 'Bari, 23/11/2022' and the project logo, which consists of the word 'project' in a lowercase sans-serif font next to a blue water drop icon with white waves. Below the logo, the subtitle reads 'demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water'. The main title is 'Project O: Analisi multi-obiettivo degli impatti del cambiamento climatico nei sistemi complessi. Il caso dimostrativo di Acquedotto Pugliese'. In the bottom right corner, it says 'Interfaccia web'. At the bottom left, there are logos for 'POLITECNICO MILANO 1863' and 'Fondazione Politecnico di Milano'. At the bottom right, the names of the team members are listed: 'Andrea Castelletti, Marco Micotti, Matteo Sangiorgio, Enrico Weber'.

The Decision Analytics Platform (DAP) is an ICT-based web platform to support Stakeholders and Decision Makers in exploring alternative Water Planning Portfolios under different hydro-climatic and socio-economic scenarios, visualizing their spatially and temporally distributed effects.

The focus is on the Apulian demo site, a very challenging application due to its complexity and spatial extension, and where greater emphasis is placed on the decision-making component of medium-term planning.

The platform offers the possibility of carrying out analyses considering different water portfolios:

- current climate and current drinking water demand, with respect to the environmental flow
- the same as previous but considering a derogation from compliance with the environmental flow
- future climate considering a new drinking water demand
- the same as previous, but considering the adoption of reuse technologies

For each combination, the platform makes it possible to evaluate the impact with respect to the indicators considered, which are currently of the overall type, therefore offering a synthesis concerning the entire system being analyzed.

From a methodological point of view, the most interesting regulation policies could be re-simulated with Aquator also to obtain distributed indicators, such as, for example, the drinking water deficit in each demand center, therefore, at the entrance to the municipal aqueducts.

The platform's landing page offers an overview of the methodology adopted for scenario generation, the main categories of actions, and the evaluation indicators.

Potentially, several planning and management actions could be analyzed to support the decisions of the AQP, the Apulia Region, and the Appennino Meridionale District Authority, which can be grouped as follows:

- Reservoir operations - Coordinated reservoir operations can play a key role in the system's reliability. In the Apulian system, there are 5 shared reservoirs, mainly parallel to each other, that is, there is no cascading effect, and hence the mass-balance dynamics can be computed separately. The release for each reservoir

is split into two or three (if, in addition to drinking and irrigation, there is also industrial use). These operations could be grouped into these two categories:

- day-by-day management policies: this is an allocation problem over time, to define the efficient daily total release from each reservoir taking into account the stochastic inflow process, but considering a fixed distribution rule between the different uses;
 - seasonal deficit allocation strategies: this problem is related to the scheduling of the distribution, conventionally carried out at the beginning of the irrigation season, in which priorities and rules of precedence are defined for any supply reductions depending on the trend of crop growth, as well as on the climatic trend.
- New loops in the water supply irrigation system, connecting non-conventional sources (wastewater plants) to the irrigation supply network - This type of action depends upon several specifications about the foreseen technology such as its scalability (that is, the volume that can be treated and integrated into the system), the costs for installation, operation, and maintenance, as well as the time when the technology can be scaled and incorporated into the system. It is also noteworthy that this option would be tested just for feasible irrigation diversions and not for drinking water supply, where there are more stringent regulations for water reuse for urban supply. Furthermore, the water diverted to farmers will consider alternative rates of water reuse corresponding to increasing investments and available technologies. This will potentially be reflected in water savings via water reuse that could be ex-post associated with different technological solutions and narrative of future technological development and upscaling potential and associated costs.
 - New loops in the drinking water distribution systems - This kind of action will also be supplemented with a few structural decisions, which are currently under consideration by the AQP authority, for instance, expanding the canal capacity in certain parts of the system and integrating alternative water sources, such as impounded sources which are not currently part of the network that could be reactivated and could increase the reliability of the system. This includes the reactivation of several wells, which provides a good opportunity to explore treatment technologies. As for the type of previous actions, also in this case it is necessary to evaluate the quantitative effects in terms of volumes that can be produced, with respect to costs.
 - Infrastructure investments - These are actions to strengthen the water supply capacity or management flexibility, such as strengthening the Occhito dam connection, doubling the pipe capacity in the Sinni scheme, and a new lift plant in Parco del Marchese purification plant.
 - Water demands change - Drinking demand is expected to change in specific areas, increasing to meet demands of foreseen touristic expansion, and the Apulia region administration could play a role in addressing this development in certain locations and not others; the same drinking demand could be changed over the time through new tariff plans; finally, the irrigation demand is also expected to change to accommodate different crop plans as well as for the expansion of drip plants and for the use of water with different quality.

A WPP is defined as a combination of different actions, related to the management of existing infrastructure, such as reservoir control, increasing infrastructure capacity, such as doubling pipeline capacity and their connections within the system, reactivating non-conventional sources such as wells that are not currently considered into the system, as well as the integration of re-use technologies in feasible small water loops, taken at a pre-defined date in the time horizon considered. All the WPPs identified are documented and analyzed in the Deliverable D4.4.

4.1.1 Outline

In order to formally define a Water Planning Portfolio, the combination of the selected actions has to be defined in terms of constraints, parameters, rules, or other quantitative information needed to run the modeling tools. The DAP allows exploring this information through a set of descriptive indicators, spatially and temporally distributed, providing a quantitative outline of the actions taken into consideration for each WPP.

An example of a hypothetical Water Planning Portfolio for the Apulian Demo site could be the following:

1. Reservoir operations: a new water deficit allocation strategy for each reservoir to increase the percentage of water reserved for human consumption;
2. New loops in the drinking water distribution systems: a number of wells in Lecce's Province are restored using an innovative treatment technology developed in Project Ô – WP2, to be activated as auxiliary sources during a shortage, reducing the dependence on main reservoirs;
3. Water demands change:
 - a. part of farmed land in the Capitanata Irrigation District is converted to drip irrigation, lowering the summer water demand of the area;
 - b. water price policies are redesigned to encourage water saving during summer, producing a lowering of the drinking water demand peak.

This hypothetical example has been labelled WPP1 on the Water Planning Portfolios page. The two buttons of the "Outline" columns allow analyzing quantitative aspects related to actions listed in the WPP description with two different visualization tools: the Outline Map and the Outline Dashboard.

The first tool is an enhanced webGIS integrated into the DAP, providing a dynamic spatial representation of WPP actions that can be managed and queried through three tabs:

- Layers: available information is organized into different layers that can be grouped, switched on and off, and styled with a customized legend.
- Tools: search functionalities to geo-locate actions on the map, a time slider to explore time dimension when relevant.
- Info: when this tab is enabled, when clicking on the map, all elements of all active layers are queried and return their attributes (key-value pairs of text or numerical, images, URL, link to files, etc.).

The second visualizing tool, the Outline Dashboard, presents several pre-defined descriptive indicators organized in an interactive Dashboard where all the most relevant features related to actions are presented with different types of charts:

- the top row contains a brief textual explanation of the action composing the specific WPP, divided into groups;
- the top chart is related to Reservoir Operation actions, showing the share of water deficit allocation among different water users, for each reservoir;
- the bottom-left chart is related to Water Demand changes, showing the expected water demand for each irrigation district, deriving from actions undertaken in WPP1, with a monthly time step;
- the bottom-right chart is also related to Water Demand changes, presenting the yearly water demand for the industry, disaggregated by Province.

4.1.2 Evaluation

The modeling tools and the optimization engines generated several simulations for different combinations of future Scenarios and WPPs. A set of evaluation indicators eventually disaggregated over time and space, will be used to assess the performances of each available combination across the time horizon.

Starting from the Water Planning Portfolios page, once selected the combination of interesting WPP and Scenario is evaluated, by using the "Select Scenario" menu under the "Evaluation", it is possible to launch two different tools: Evaluation Map and Evaluation Charts.

The Evaluation Map is targeted to provide the spatial representation of indicators. It relies on the same webGIS functionalities of the Outline Map, but it is empowered by an indicator selector (in the Tools tab) that allows switching among different indicators, eventually exploring them also in time, with the time slider.

The second tool, Evaluation Charts, is a dynamic page where some indicators are pre-loaded but that can be extended or customized by adding more indicators to the page or even switching among different combinations of WPP and Scenarios.

4.1.3 Comparison

Once defined and evaluated, each single WPP, the Comparison page allows extending the analysis to different combinations of WPPs and Scenarios across different indicators.

When multiple interests are competing for the use of a scarce resource, Decision Makers should encompass in the analysis a few different evaluation indicators, trying to identify trade-offs and compromise solutions able to gain wide support among Stakeholders.

Starting from the Water Planning Portfolios page, all the interesting WPPs and Scenarios can be selected for comparison with the toggle switcher placed under the "Comparison" column. The Comparison page is activated by hitting the "Compare selected" button, presenting a Parallel Coordinates chart populated with data coming from selected WPPs and Scenarios.

This kind of chart is a very useful support tool for trade-off identification and analysis: each combination of WPP and Scenario is represented with a broken line, while indicators considered are placed one for each parallel vertical axes. The intersections between a line and the axes, therefore, represent indicator values for a specific WPP-Scenario combination.

Indicators are those presented previously, aggregated over time, and cumulated in space. Values represented could be expressed in physical units, or as "Normalized values" (e.g., ranging from 0 to 1), by clicking on the related toggle switcher.

The chart on the Comparison page is also interactive, allowing iteratively filtering over different axis to explore trade-offs and single out the most interesting WPP-Scenario combination. Once identified, the most interesting combination can also be selected and saved for future reference. By clicking on a line, the related WPP-Scenario combination is selected and added to the related list at the bottom. Finally, the toggle switcher allows moving from a visualization with all the available combinations to another one with only those selected.

4.1.4 Architecture

The Decision Analytic Platform was developed with a stack of open-source software, mixing mature and well-known solutions with customized software components to provide the features described above.

The idea is to build a virtual machine containing all the software needed to run the platform that could also be easily installed, moved, and replicated anywhere. Considering this target and the requirements mentioned above, the stack used for DAP development uses the same components as the one under development for the User Collaborative Platform (see report D7.3 for more details):

- Vagrant as Virtualization Environment: a tool for building, managing, and distributing virtual machines;
- Ansible as Provisioner, used by Vagrant to install and update software and configurations on the virtual machine;
- Virtualbox, a Virtual Machine application to create the virtual machine itself;
- Ubuntu Server as Operating System, equipped with a LAPP software bundle, an acronym for Linux, Apache as Web Server, PostgreSQL + PostGIS as GeoDatabase, PHP as the web programming language, the base of Drupal;
- QGIS Server as Map Server for publishing maps and other spatial contents of the DAP;
- Drupal as Content Management System.

5 Comments and remarks

The meeting was organized to provide a direct, though empirical, validation of the Project Ô tools by interacting with the potential final users. Specifically, the goal was to understand to which extent these tools are ready-to-be-used, which improvement or expansion are needed to fully characterize the spatio-temporal heterogeneity of the currently modelled process and if new processes are to be included in the future. The discussion between the participants started with the Puglia Region regarding the level of simplification of the models used and the replicability of the techniques adopted.

AQP specified the differences between the original model of the adduction system and the reduced one. In the first, all the main components are represented, as well as existing constraints and rules. In the surrogate, on the other hand, a synthesis of this complexity is offered to have a vision at a higher decision-making level. In this way, the possibility of understanding in detail what happens in the system at the management level is inevitably lost.

POLIMI recalls how in the reduced model, the spatial dimension is completely lost and therefore, it is not possible to represent where any deficits are concentrated and why.

District Authority underlines how the reduced model can be used as a first approximation but how the detailed one is needed to verify the consequences of the effects in a more precise way.

AQP recalls how, at the decision-making table, a summary representation is needed on the various aspects. AQP also recalls how the guidelines for the future planning of aqueduct networks explicitly require tools to verify the impact of each work within an integrated system, and for this reason, a system such as the one produced by Project Ô can be fundamental to support strategic planning

However, the District Authority highlights a limitation of the system: if the drinking water was represented starting from detailed information (the Aquator model), this is not the case for the irrigation part (and for the industrial part, even if less relevant). The risk, therefore, is to rely on a tool that provides a different type of detail and precision. It also confirms that the level of detail of Aquator is excessive in the planning phase, therefore, a similar tool that could be decisive on a planning and scheduling scale in the provision of resources is very useful.

POLIMI recalls the purpose and the boundaries of the system. In the original idea, the analysis had to focus on the case of the aqueduct in order to evaluate the impact of the reactivation of a single dismissed well. Subsequently, since the water resource stored in the reservoirs is shared between the drinking, irrigation, and industrial sectors, we have extended the system to include also the two missing sectors. Only in this way, indeed, is it possible to have a realistic description of the dynamics occurring in the real system. In general, the tool can be easily extended to include a more accurate description of the irrigation sector.

AQP confirms that the focus of Project Ô was precisely the use of unconventional water. In certain emergency conditions, it can be assumed to activate the treatment of the water coming from some wells that normally cannot be used. It also highlights how, for irrigation systems, once demand has been reconstructed, it is not that necessary to have more details, as is the case for drinking water. Remember that in Aquator, there are rules for simulating reservoirs, which also consider the irrigation needs over time

The District Authority confirms that, at the planning level, it may be sufficient to consider an aggregate demand by area or by sub-system, to evaluate the allocation of the different sectors according to availability and availability forecasts. It is necessary to think about average data to set up evaluation rules, as, in fact, it already happens but without models, starting from the availability of water and evaluating the possibility of allocation and consequent impacts.

We then moved on to the type of support offered by the tools developed.

AQP argues that, at the beginning of the year, the water availability could be estimated and what are the possible ways of allocation and, therefore the resulting deficits.

District Authority highlights how a portfolio, that is, each line shown in a parallel plot, represents the effects of a different distribution policy considering a 10-year horizon in the past. But how to use this result in the future? At the beginning of the 2023 irrigation season, when the negotiating tables between the stakeholders will start in which everyone asks for their availability, what does the model tell us? Today we do so with a series of projections

and empirical mechanisms to define the disbursement decisions. Seasonal hydrological forecasts would be needed, which would provide more solid elements to plan on. It would become interesting for us to integrate this into the model, rather than the SPI conditions of recent months, and to understand what the situation of the system is and what effects could be expected depending on the distribution.

POLIMI recalls how the project aimed to evaluate the potential of reuse by comparing the current and future situation, bearing in mind the consequences of climate change. The platform already makes it possible to support medium and long-term planning decisions, such as increasing availability by integrating unconventional water sources into the system or verifying the impact of a new drinking demand model due to the expansion of tourist accommodation facilities, or the modification of environmental outflows. However, it should be strengthened to support management decisions such as scheduling irrigation seasons, integrating online information to update system status, and providing forecasts of inflow trends.

The District Authority highlights how it would be important to be able to consider other types of intervention, such as the enhancement of reservoir capacity or the connection of other surface sources through new inlets.

POLIMI recalls how the structural investments on the AQP supply network could be integrated by building adequate reduced models of new Aquator instances, while in the case of external interventions, the integrated model should be extended so that it can adequately also represent those parts of the irrigation network subject to changes.

The Capitanata Consortium, underlining the potential of this type of tools and their reusability in other contexts, takes up the management discourse underlining that the concept of irrigation season must also be dynamized, given that in recent years there has been an evident extension of it.

POLIMI adds that the use of the soil could also constitute an input to the model, thus being able to respond also to progressive modifications of the crops present, also under the qualitative characteristics of the reused water that could help to guide the type of irrigated crops.

District Authority and AQP take up the regulatory theme relating to the reuse of water, recalling that these are constantly evolving issues in a framework that is not yet clear.

In conclusion, POLIMI recalls that the tools developed are technological solutions that can serve not only to answer the issues addressed in the project but are modular and can also support other analyses.

AQP emphasizes the importance of a flexible approach, given that the peculiarity of the Apulian system is precisely the interconnection of the system, which guarantees greater resilience to climate change.

On the topic, POLIMI mentions the prospect of a new division within the Mediterranean Centre for Climate Change (CMSCC), tentatively referred to as "intelligent technology for climate transition". The basic idea of the new division is to create a structure that provides assessments on how the technology can be exploited from the design point of view (efficiency parameters, costs, ..., typical of engineering design) in complex contexts where integration is essential to provide a broader view.

AQP and the Puglia Region declare themselves to be very interested and propose to plan a dialogue with the top levels of their respective structures to explore synergies and opportunities.

Appendix 1

H2020-CIRC-2017 - 776816

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Bari, 23/11/2022

demonstration of planning and technology tools for a
circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water

Project O: Analisi multi-obiettivo degli
impatti del cambiamento climatico nei
sistemi complessi. Il caso dimostrativo di
Acquedotto Pugliese

Inquadramento metodologico

POLITECNICO
MILANO 1863

Fondazione
Politecnico
di Milano

Andrea Castelletti, Marco Micotti, Matteo Sangiorgio, Enrico Weber

IN UN MONDO IN TRANSFORMAZIONE: CRESCe LA DOMANDA DI RISORSE

contesto

project O

IL CAMBIAMENTO CLIMATICO AUMENTA LA FREQUENZA DEGLI EVENTI ESTREMI

contesto

approccio

project O

acquedotto pugliese

l'acqua, bene comune

- 22,500 km di rete di adduzione
- 11,000 km di rete di scarichi
- 182 impianti di trattamento
- >4 milioni di utenti

Un caso emblematico per dimensione, complessità e condivisione delle risorse

il demo-site

condizioni climatiche

condizioni socio-economiche

le condizioni cambiano

project

Elaborato	N.
Carta della Significatività delle Pressioni per le Acque Sotterranee: Uso Agricolo	
Scala 1: 600.000	

Legenda

Classi Significatività Uso Agricolo

- Alta
- Media
- Bassa
- Molto Bassa
- Pressione assente o dato non disponibile
- limite regionale
- limite Distretto Idrografico
- Idrografia principale

Per rispondere alle sfide del clima e a fabbisogni crescenti occorrono disponibilità aggiuntive e strumenti di supporto decisionale

come decidere?

Water Portfolios

Utility Managers
Water Regulators

Business

Stakeholders

piattaforme collaborative

Decisional Analytic Platform (DAP): il framework per supportare decisioni pianificatorie

DAP

project

SISTEMA

Obiettivi di ottimizzazione:

1. Deficit Irrigui
2. Deficit Industriale
3. Deficit potabile
4. Costi AQP di distribuzione

Obiettivo complessivo:

L'integrazione di fonti idriche non convenzionali posso garantire la soddisfazione dei fabbisogni future tenendo conto del cambiamento climatico?

MODELLO STRATEGICO

DAP

AQP DSS (aquator)

MODELLO RIDOTTO

Generazione degli Scenari

Framework decisionale

Porfolio di adattamento e mitigazione

DAP

project

Generazione degli Scenari

Per ogni fonte idrica (grandi invasi e sorgenti):

Variabili meteo «downscaled» (es. temperatura, precipitazione)

Framework decisionale

- 2 scenari climatici: RCP 4.5 e RCP 8.5
- 2 orizzonti futuri: 2040-2050 e 2090-2100
- 2 domande potabili: attuale e da sviluppo regionale
- 2 scenari di fonti non convenzionali: acqua di riuso da affinamento, riabilitazione di pozzi

DAP

project

Porfolio di adattamento e mitigazione

The management strategy can be adapted progressively, depending on dynamics of the system.

DAP

Come valutare i portfolio?

**Portfolio = una
nuova auto**

portfolio

Come valutare i portfolio?
=
Come scegliere l'auto?

portfolio

Come valutare i portfolio?
=
Come scegliere l'auto?

Come valutare i portfolio?
=
Come scegliere l'auto?

Come valutare i portfolio?

=

Come scegliere l'auto?

portfolio

project

Come valutare i portfolio?

=

Come scegliere l'auto?

Gli assi rappresentano indicatori

portfolio

Come valutare i portfolio?

=

Come scegliere l'auto?

Gli assi rappresentano indicatori

portfolio

Come valutare i portfolio?

=

Come scegliere l'auto?

Ideale...

Gli assi rappresentano indicatori

portfolio

project

Preferenze crescenti

Come valutare i portfolio?

=

Come scegliere l'auto?

...possibile

Gli assi rappresentano indicatori

portfolio

Preferenze crescenti

Come valutare i portfolio?
=
Come scegliere l'auto?

ogni spezzata
individua un portfolio

portfolio

Preferenze crescenti

DAP

project

- Data: time series, maps, ...
- Indicators computation
- Plot API
- Map server
- Web interface

ict4water.eu

piattaforme collaborative

project

Project Ô – DAP

Decision Analytic Platform

ABOUT DAP

The Decision Analytic Platform is a tool developed within Project Ô - Circular Water Solutions for Sustainable Development Goals 6 and 12 on Clean Water and Sanitation & Responsible Consumption and Production.

The main goal of this platform is to improve the resilience of a community (at hydrological basin-scale) supporting water authorities to enhance wastewater, e.g. by selecting and adopting the proper technology to reconnect polluted wells to the water main distribution network, or by exploiting refined water from wastewater treatment plants to irrigate suitable crops.

id	irrigation def.	Drinking Water def.	Distribution Costs	Industrial def.	WPP	Scenario	uid_from_uid
44983544	76938760	45801555	1387789	WPP2	r1q4_5_2050	11	null
84250510	9935950	4233815	4603370	WPP2	r1q4_5_2050	11	null

DAP

project Ô

<http://eu-project-o.eu>

@EUProjectO

/EUProjectO

grazie per l'attenzione

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H2020-CIRC-2017 - 776816

Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Appendix 2

demonstration of planning and technology tools for a
circular, integrated and symbiotic use of water

Project O: Analisi multi-obiettivo degli
impatti del cambiamento climatico nei
sistemi complessi. Il caso dimostrativo di
Acquedotto Pugliese

Aspetti modellistici e
implementativi

Riduzione della complessità (schema Ofanto)

SCHEMA DI DISTRIBUZIONE			
UTENTE	DERIVAZIONE	Portata in mc./sec.	
		Massima	Media
Consorzio di Bonifica della "CAPITANATA"	Diga Marana Capaciotti	6	1,2
Consorzio di Bonifica "VULTURE ED ALTO BRADANO"	Canale Ofanto - Rendina	4	1,5
	Gaudiano	1	0,3
Consorzio di Bonifica "TERRE D'APULIA"	Cefalicchio	1	0,3
	Vasca di calma	4,2	0,15
	Diga Locone	8	2

PLANIMETRIA GENERALE INVASI E SCHEMI IDRICI E.I.P.L.I.

LEGENDA

- Schema Idrico Ionico - Sinsi
- Schema Idrico Basento - Bradano
- Schema Idrico Ofanto
- Schema Idrico Taro
- Invasi gestiti dall'E.I.P.L.I.
- Invasi gestiti da altri Enti
- ◆ Traversa

reti di distribuzione

Riduzione della complessità (schema Agri-Sinni)

reti di distribuzione

project Ô

Riduzione della complessità (grandi vettori acquedotto)

water storage system

water distribution system

reti di distribuzione

project Ô

water storage system

grandi invasi ad uso multiplo

modello "ridotto" di AQP

water distribution system

rete neurale
artificiale

modello strategico

Stima delle disponibilità:

- modello degli afflussi agli invasi
- modello delle sorgenti naturali

Stima dei fabbisogni:

- domande irrigue di riferimento ad ogni invaso
- domanda industriale all'invaso di Monte Cotugno
- domanda potabile

Dati meteo disponibili e indici

Meteo & soil	
Daily precipitation	from 1950 to 2018
Daily temperature	from 1950 to 2018
Daily runoff	from 1979 to 2019
Monthly soil moisture	from 2007 to 2019
Drought index	
Monthly SPI	from 1950 to 2018
Monthly SPEI	from 1950 to 2018
Monthly SRI	from 1979 to 2019
Natural springs (Cassano, Caposele)	
Daily withdrawal	from 2006 to 2019
Reservoirs (Fortore, Pertusillo, Sinni, Locone, Conza)	
Daily storage	from 2000 to 2019 (NO 2015)
Daily net drinking withdrawal	from 2000 to 2004
Daily gross drinking withdrawal	from 2006 to 2019
Daily total release from Pertusillo	from 2017 to 2019
Groundwater (wells)	
Daily gross drinking withdrawal	from 2013 to 2020
Other sources (watermakers - desalters)	
Yearly total volume	1999,2005,2006,2008,2011

raccolta dati

Afflussi agli invasi ottenuti da chiusura di bilancio [elaborazione da dati forniti da AQP, Consorzi e ARPA]

disponibilità

project Ô

Relazioni autorità di bacino

raccolta dati

project Ô

Fabbisogni stimati a partire da forniture storiche

[elaborazione da dati forniti da AQP, Consorzi e R. Puglia]

fabbisogni

Modello di simulazione dei grandi invasi

	Occhito	Conza	Locone	Pertusillo	Monte Cotugno
Localization	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Catchment area	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Live storage	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Dead storage	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Maximum operating level	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Crest elevation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Environmental flow	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Level-Storage curve	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

modelli

project Ô

Modello ridotto della rete dei grandi vettori di AQP

1. Creazione di **serie sintetiche** di portate immesse alla rete (dagli invasi e dalle sorgenti)
 2. Costruzione di un **modello completo** della rete di distribuzione sostituendo gli invasi con degli ingressi (catchments)
 3. Uso delle serie sintetiche per simulare l'**allocazione ottimale** prodotta da Aquator
 4. Elaborazione dei **risultati di Aquator**:
 - deficit complessivo
 - costi complessivi
1. Addestramento di una **rete neurale**

modelli

project O

Accuratezza del modello ridotto della rete dei grandi vettori di AQP

Coefficiente R^2 :

- Deficit 0.998
- Costi 0.996

modelli

modello strategico

project Ô

- **Domanda irrigua, industriale e potabile:** Attuale, Futura
- **Adozione di tecnologie di riuso:** Si, No
- **Clima:** Attuale, RCP4.5, RCP8.5
- **Orizzonte temporale:** 2010-19, 2050-59, 2090-99
- **Vincolo sul DA:** Attivo, Inattivo

Caratteristiche:

- Domanda irrigua, industriale e potabile **Attuale**
- Adozione di tecnologie di riuso **No**
- Clima **Attuale**
- Orizzonte temporale **2010-19**
- Vincolo sul DA **Attivo**

baseline

Livello dei grandi invasi e deficit simulati

Occhito
Locone
Conza
Pertusillo
Monte C.

baseline

project Ô

Impatto del rispetto del DA sui deficit potabile, irriguo e industriale.

Serbatoio	DA [m ³ /s]	DA [Mm ³ /anno]
Occhito	1.78	56.14
Locone	0.07	2.1
Conza	0.05	1.54
Pertusillo	0.75	23.65
Monte Cotugno	0.53	16.6

baseline

Livello dei grandi invasi e deficit simulati

baseline

project Ô

modello strategico

- **Domanda irrigua, industriale e potabile:** Attuale, Futura
- **Adozione di tecnologie di riuso:** Si, No
- **Clima:** Attuale, RCP4.5, RCP8.5
- **Orizzonte temporale:** 2010-19, 2050-59, 2090-99
- **Vincolo sul DA:** Attivo, Inattivo

I processi di afflusso ad ogni grande invaso e le disponibilità delle sorgenti naturali sono modellati utilizzando delle reti neurali ricorrenti (LSTM).

Input: precipitazione, temperatura
 Output: afflusso

scenari climatici

project Ô

Esempio: afflusso del Pertusillo nel periodo di addestramento (2010-19).

Periodo di controllo

Proiezione

scenari climatici

I modelli degli afflussi sono poi utilizzati per calcolare le proiezioni future delle disponibilità in un decennio vicino (2050-59) e uno lontano (2090-99)

Dati relativi al Pertusillo

scenari climatici

Effetto del DA in uno scenario climatico attuale e futuro (RCP 8.5, 2050-59).

Politica di compromesso

confronto

modello strategico

- Domanda irrigua, industriale e potabile: Attuale, Futura
- Adozione di tecnologie di riuso: Si, No
- Clima: Attuale, RCP4.5, RCP8.5
- Orizzonte temporale: 2010-19, 2050-59, 2090-99
- Vincolo sul DA: Attivo, Inattivo

Le proiezioni della domanda potabile per i prossimi decenni prevedono una maggior richiesta, specialmente nella zona costiera e nel periodo estivo.

L'incremento annuo complessivo previsto è nell'ordine di 80.9 Mm³.

domanda
potabile futura

Effetto combinato della nuova **domanda potabile** e del **clima futuro** (RCP 4.5 e 8.5 per i decenni 2050-59 e 2090-99).

Politica di compromesso

confronto

modello strategico

project Ô

- Domanda irrigua, industriale e potabile: Attuale, Futura
- Adozione di tecnologie di riuso: Si, No
- Clima: Attuale, RCP4.5, RCP8.5
- Orizzonte temporale: 2010-19, 2050-59, 2090-99
- Vincolo sul DA: Attivo, Inattivo

Acqua di affinamento

Reclamation	Operative	Use of the reclaimed water	Managed by	Distribution operated by	Capacity of the plant	Situation of the ground water
Trinitapoli	Yes	Agriculture	AQP	Consorzio di Bonifica della Capitanata	7,200 m ³ /day	Critical conditions
San Severo	No, to be operative soon	Agriculture	AQP	Consorzio di Bonifica della Capitanata	n.a.	Critical conditions
Ostuni	Yes	Agriculture	AQP	Municipality of Ostuni	9,867 m ³ /day	Critical conditions
Fasano	Yes	Agriculture and environmental	Aquasoil, contracted out by Municipality	Aquasoil, contracted out by Municipality	7,680 m ³ /day	Critical conditions
Taranto Bellavista	No, under adjustment	Industrial	AQP	-	>> 10,000 m ³ /day (treatment)	Critical conditions
Taranto Gennarini	No, under adjustment	Industrial/Agriculture	AQP	-	30,000 m ³ /day (treatment)	Critical conditions
	Yes	Agriculture	AQP	Corsano Municipality	2,000 m ³ /day	n.a.
Gallipoli	Yes	Agricoltura/irrigazione	AQP	Consorzio	12,000 m ³ /day	Still present

(*)

Table 12. Classification of the reclamation plants according to selected characteristic

riuso

project

(*) E. Cagno, P. Garrone, A. Neri, A. Rizzuni

Integrazioni irrigue da acqua di affinamento

	[m ³ /s]	[Mm ³ /anno]
Occhito irr	1.0	31.54
Locone irr	0.125	3.94
Conza irr	0.04	1.26
Pertusillo irr	0.18	5.68
Monte Cotugno irr	0.22	6.94
Monte Cotugno ind (*)	0.4	12.61
Totale	1.965	61.97

(*) si ipotizza che l'apporto di acqua di riuso (o da altre fonti superficiali) soddisfi completamente il fabbisogno.

riuso

project

Reinclusione nette disponibilità di pozzi abbandonati

riuso

project

Effetto dell'adozione di tecnologie di riuso e reinclusione dei pozzi attualmente dismessi.

confronto

Deficit nel caso in cui vengano adottate politiche di compromesso.

confronto

project

<http://eu-project-o.eu>

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grazie per l'attenzione

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Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
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Appendix 3

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Horizon 2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

Bari, 23/11/2022

demonstration of planning and technology tools for a circular,
integrated and symbiotic use of water

Project O: Analisi multi-obiettivo degli impatti
del cambiamento climatico nei sistemi
complessi. Il caso dimostrativo di
Acquedotto Pugliese

Interfaccia web

POLITECNICO
MILANO 1863

Fondazione
Politecnico
di Milano

Andrea Castelletti, **Marco Micotti**, Matteo Sangiorgio, Enrico Weber

Time series

Scenarios

Indicators

Maps

- Minimum Environmental Flow
- Reservoir management
- Water demand for Irrigation
- Drinking Water

Actions

- Outline of **Water planning portfolios** features
- **Evaluation** of Water planning portfolios across different scenarios
- **Comparison** of different combination of Portfolios and scenarios

DAP

project

Project Ö - DAP

Decision Analytic Platform

ABOUT DAP

The Decision Analytic Platform is a tool developed within Project Ö - Circular Water Solutions for Sustainable Development Goals 6 and 12 on Clean Water and Sanitation & Responsible Consumption and Production.

The main goal of this platform is to improve the resilience of a community (at hydrological basin-scale) supporting water authorities to enhance wastewater, e.g. by selecting and adopting the proper technology to reconnect polluted wells to the water main distribution network, or by exploiting refined water from wastewater treatment plants to irrigate suitable crops.

Light data science platform to browse DAP outcomes:

- **Scenarios** considered
- Features of **Water planning portfolios**
- **Evaluation** of Water planning portfolios across different scenarios
- **Comparison** of different combination of Portfolios and scenarios

DAP

ABOUT

DAP CONCEPT

GO TO PLATFORM

Project Ô - DAP

Decision Analytic Platform

ABOUT DAP

The Decision Analytic Platform is a tool developed within Project Ô - Circular Water Solutions for Sustainable Development Goals 6 and 12 on Clean Water and Sanitation & Responsible Consumption and Production.

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<https://xake.deib.polimi.it:8080/dap/>

Demo

Data: time series,
maps, ...

Indicators
computation

Plot
API

Map
server

Web
interface

Users

Architecture

 Data: time series, maps, ...

 Indicators computation

 Plot API

 Map server

 Web interface

 Users

Architecture

Light data science platform

- combine easy to use **Content Management System (CMS)**, advanced **computational tools** and **interactive data and maps visualizations**
- **High flexibility and customization**: computational tools can be external or internal, with different integration levels
- Software as a Service (SaaS): **cloud-based platform**, easy to set up and maintain
- **Integrated scenario analysis**: local scale assessments of planning decisions under different large scale/global scenarios, multi-sectorial indicators, spatial / temporally distributed data analysis and visualization

Strength

Short term

- User activation & Test
- User survey: <https://po-usability.methodsinnovation.org/>
- Software release
- Dataset publication on Zenodo

Next Steps

<http://eu-project-o.eu>

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